

CERCA

**Comunidad de Energías Renovables de
la Comarca de Calatayud**

**[Regional Energy Community
Description]**

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1. Introduction

CERCA is a regional renewable energy community (REC) operating in the Calatayud County (Aragón), a vast region covering 2,500 km² and comprising 67 small municipalities which, like other regions in Spain, faces the problem of rural depopulation. The initiative came from the region's own residents who, concerned about the future of their villages, decided to set up this REC to combat depopulation and sustain the region's economic activity through the production of distributed clean energy.

CERCA aims to give the Calatayud region control over its own energy supply. It is made up of residents, local businesses, associations, companies, and local councils who share a simple vision: to produce clean, local, and fair energy.

The initiative is driven by individuals dedicated to the future of their villages, who are convinced that by collaborating, they can create a more dynamic and sustainable region. CERCA aims to make energy a real opportunity by reducing costs, strengthening the local economy, and caring for the environment.

The energy community is open to all: regional residents, members of associations or part of a business, everyone is welcome to join a model in which energy is shared and managed collectively, thereby giving CERCA greater autonomy.

Figure 1: Calatayud County map.

2. *Brief overview of its conception*

The Renewable Energy Community of the Calatayud Region, "CERCA" was born out of concern among a group of residents of the Calatayud Region for the future of their villages in the face of depopulation and the relocation of their companies. Calatayud is located in one of the regions of the so-called empties Spain.

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of municipal population in the Comarca Comunidad de Calatayud (2025).
Data obtained from INE

This concern prompted them to visit the Photovoltaic Systems Research Group at the Solar Energy Institute of the Technical University of Madrid (IES-UPM), where they asked the following questions: Could energy communities contribute to the future of our villages? If so, how could they help us?

Through the JALON consortium, which comprises research institutions, local organisations in the Calatayud region, and a legal expert, they concluded that renewable energy communities could indeed contribute to reverse the trend of depopulation in their villages, provided they met certain criteria:

1. *Regional energy community*: a single large-scale energy community in the region to facilitate self-production and shared consumption of energy from photovoltaic systems to be installed in the various villages in the region with technical solutions at the village level and technical solutions at the regional level.
2. *Establishment through participatory processes*: The underlying motivation behind the new energy community promoted by the European Commission is for citizens to actively participate in the energy transition by self-producing and self-consuming clean electricity, but also by changing their energy habits to become "close to zero-emission citizens." Therefore, a genuine energy community must be established through participatory processes involving the citizens themselves, and in this case, within the Region. This ensures that the design of the energy community, the levels of participation, the organization, and the technical and legal solutions respond to their needs and initiatives.
3. *Real participation*: In addition to participatory processes, the litmus test of real participation is the funding. Therefore, at least 40% of the investment in the energy community's photovoltaic installations will be made through microinvestments from residents, municipalities, businesses, industries, and associations that wish to

participate. These microinvestments are the key to entering the energy community. Investment will not only be required in photovoltaic installations, but also in land and other goods and services necessary for self-production and self-consumption.

4. *Members of the regional energy community:* The future of the region's villages has several dimensions, such as the social and environmental, but when the people of the region express their concerns, they are primarily referring to the loss of population, economic activity, and employment. For self-generation and self-consumption of electricity at the regional level to materialize into sustainable economic activity and to establish a stable population, it is absolutely essential that all stakeholders in the region participate, including economic stakeholders: residents, town councils, businesses, industries, and associations.
5. *Promoting regulatory changes:* As expected, the regional energy community has been established in accordance with current legislation, particularly with regard to shared self-consumption. However, participatory processes should discuss the regulatory changes that should be demanded and promoted to adapt the regulations to the specificities of the decentralized rural areas of the emptied Spain.

Creating a single regional energy community has many advantages over each town creating its own community:

- On the one hand, it greatly *simplifies the administrative procedures* for establishing and managing the community: there is only one energy community for the entire region, so all administrative management is simplified.
- On the other hand, *lower prices can be obtained* by purchasing photovoltaic systems together. We even plan to train local installers and electricians to undertake projects in the region.
- Third, *technical specifications and quality control procedures* can be implemented to ensure the quality of the components and photovoltaic systems installed in the region. In a context of a boom in self-consumption photovoltaic installations, poor implementation is a real risk.
- Fourthly, *resources can be used much more efficiently* by pooling energy production and consumption across the region.
- Fifthly, it allows the *promotion of economic, social and environmental projects* at the regional level that would otherwise be impossible.
- And finally, *villages* that, due to their *small size* and management capacity, could not do so alone, *can benefit from this opportunity*.

Due to the decentralized nature of rural areas, fragmented solutions are often proposed by village to address problems that are common to all. However, a joint regional solution, on a larger scale, allows objectives to be achieved more quickly and with greater impact.

What's needed, in return, is organizational capacity. And this is the great asset of a single energy community in the Calatayud region: it can act as a driver to organize its 67 towns and 101 associations.

3. CERCA legal constitution

During the establishment phase of the energy community, discussions were held about what legal form it should take. The JALON project members recommended setting it up as a foundation because it best preserved the principles that motivated the initiative and ensured member participation. However, the promoters opted for the legal form of a non-profit cooperative. Despite negative experiences of this type of business in the region, it was considered the most democratic option.

Figure 3: CERCA's logo

4. Participation models

Within the framework of the JALON project, the participation models for citizens, associations, businesses, companies and town councils in the CERCA cooperative were developed.

The main design criterion for CERCA's participation models is that the REC should adapt to the needs and specific characteristics of its potential participants (citizens, associations, businesses, companies, and municipalities) and to the dispersed rural environment, and not the other way around. Furthermore, these participation models seek to attract, through multi-level participation, individuals and legal entities close to the production facilities to a more intense participation in the REC and its projects.

Based on this criterion, there are six participation models. These are arranged according to the participation of local stakeholders in the REC, from most intense to least intense. In this sense, they range from a model of full membership and participation in the REC to a model of participation through mere capital investment in the project:

- *Model 1: CERCA member contributing rights and/or money to permit and/or finance CERCA-owned PV installations:* The participant becomes a member of the CERCA cooperative and also makes a contribution of money, rights, or assets to provide the REC with resources to carry out its photovoltaic installations. In return, they receive remuneration in energy or money.
- *Model 2: CERCA member owning their own PV installation and contributing their surplus energy to the REC:* The participant becomes a member of the CERCA cooperative and owns their own PV installation. This installation is not transferred to the REC, but the REC, which sometimes acts as a retailer, manages the member's surplus energy.
- *Model 3: Collaborator owns his own PV installation and contributes his surplus energy to the REC:* The participant does not become a member of the CERCA cooperative but is the owner of his own PV installation. This installation is not transferred to the REC, but the REC, which sometimes acts as a retailer, manages the participant's surplus energy.
- *Model 4: CERCA member supplied by the REC:* The participant becomes a CERCA member, but neither makes a contribution nor has its own PV plants. CERCA, as a retailer, supplies its electricity at a reduced price.
- *Model 5: Collaborator supplied by the REC:* The participant neither becomes a member of the REC, nor contributes, nor has its own PV plants. CERCA, as a retailer, supplies its electricity at a reduced price provided that the participant lives near the territory where CERCA operates.

- *Model 6: Investor collaborator in CERCA's activity:* The participant does not acquire CERCA member status. Their only participation in the REC is to invest capital in CERCA's activity.

These models are structured along two main axes. The first axis distinguishes between Models I-II and IV, on the one hand, and III and V-VI, on the other. In this sense, the first two involve more intense cooperation with the REC, since the participants are CERCA members. In contrast, collaboration in Models III and V-VI does not require CERCA membership.

The second axis through which these models are structured is the contribution to the REC. In this sense, in Model I, the member makes a contribution that allows the CERCA to develop its own PV projects. In Models II and III, the member/collaborator has its own facility and contributes only its surplus to the CERCA. Finally, in Models IV and V, the collaborator only receives renewable energy produced by the CERCA, and in Model VI, the collaborator only invests money in CERCA's activities in exchange for future remuneration.

The models are described and analysed in more depth in the document at the following link:

<https://jalon-ce.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/CERCA-Participation-models-ES.pdf>

5. *Self-consumption and electricity marketing company*

It is worth mentioning that CERCA is a cooperative that will also be established as an electricity supplier. CERCA requires this dual status, as both a REC and a supplier, because the REC status, which originates in European Union law, has not been properly implemented in Spain. Consequently, many of the activities that, according to European regulations, this entity could carry out are not currently possible under the legal regime applicable to RECs. To resolve this situation, at least until the regulations applicable to RECs are supplemented, it is necessary to establish CERCA as a supplier (electricity marketing company) in order to carry out the activities necessary to develop the REC. Otherwise, under current regulations, the REC would be limited to only shared self-consumption.

As REC, CERCA will carry out individual and collective photovoltaic self-consumption, with and without simplified compensation in the bill, as well as medium-sized photovoltaic plants for sale to the market or for point-to-point sales through PPA contracts.

On the other hand, becoming an electricity marketing company will also allow CERCA to connect with participants who have chosen to retain ownership of their energy-producing facilities instead of transferring them to CERCA. In this case, the cooperative may acquire ownership representation—but not ownership—of the facilities and act as a producer in relation to them. In this way, CERCA will be able to structure the sharing of surplus energy produced by the facility through shared self-consumption with other REC members.

Due to the multifaceted nature of CERCA and the different legal regimes that apply to each type of entity in the electrical system, it will be necessary in the different participation models to differentiate between the activity carried out by CERCA as a REC, those carried out as an electricity retailer, and those carried out as a producer. In the case of CERCA's activity as a producer, it will also be necessary to differentiate between cases in which the cooperative is the owner and holder of the production facilities and those in which it only holds ownership representation.

A detailed explanation of self-consumption, REC, and marketing within the current regulatory framework and their relationship with the various participation models proposed can be found in the downloadable document at the following link:

<https://jalon-ce.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/CERCA-Participation-models-ES.pdf>

6. Some key figures from CERCA

CERCA, as a REC, is already present in 15 municipalities in the region, with 18 different photovoltaic systems totaling 825 kWp and involving 150 residents, businesses, industries, and town councils. The energy generated by the REC is shared among 180 CUPS (energy meter identifiers). The total investment has been more than €625,000.

The following table summarises the photovoltaic project that has been completed:

	Installation	Power (kWp)	Village	Cost (€)	Participants	Quantity	CUPS
1	CHERRYWORLD	104,4	Munébrega	63.565,50 €	Industry	1	1
2	CODOS	72,6	Codos	65.033,79 €	Collective	15	20
3	EMPRESA MEDIAVEGA	69,85	Calatayud	38.713,85 €	Collective	4	4
4	RUESCA	29,97	Ruesca	22.926,04 €	Collective	14	17
5	MIEDES DE ARAGÓN	22,2	Miedes de Aragón	17.497,10 €	Collective	8	9
6	CARENAS	97,68	Carenas	84.134,40 €	Collective	6	6
7	BUBIERCA	44	Bubierca	30.205,18 €	Collective	17	18
8	POZUELARIZA	11	Pozuel de Ariza	7.736,49 €	Collective	9	10
9	MUNÉBREGA	16,5	Munébrega	15.298,62 €	Collective	9	12
10	ASOCIACIÓN AMIBIL	64,5	Calatayud	40.693,59 €	Association	1	1
11	MALUENDA + RAÍCES IBÉRICAS	116,48	Maluenda	88.039,63 €	Industry and collective	24	25
12	CERVERA CAÑADA	12,3	Cervera de la Cañada	15.157,81 €	Collective	7	10
13	VALTORRES	35,2	Valtorres	24.657,13 €	Collective	9	10
14	ARIZA	15	Ariza	13.158,17 €	Collective	1	4
15	URBANIZACIÓN GOLF	6,82	Calatayud	5.935,00 €	Individual	1	1
16	BELMONTE	14,175	Bemonte	15.724,38 €	Collective	8	9
17	MEDINACELI PUEBLO	83,655	Medinaceli	68.076,31 €	Collective	15	20
18	TORRIJO	8,8	Torrijo de la Cañada	9.010,72 €	Collective	1	3
	TOTAL	825,13		625.563,71 €		150	180

Some technical details from each project can be found in <https://bemaps.unizar.es/user-map/6787c7e9c8c0ee023dcda2d7/view>. Figure 4 shows the location of PV projects:

Figure 4: Distribution of CERCA PV projects in the Calatayud region and Medinaceli municipality. Source: <https://bemaps.unizar.es/user-map/6787c7e9c8c0ee023dcda2d7/view>

CERCA, as an electricity retailer, is utilizing surplus energy and supplying 100% renewable electricity. As of the date of writing this document (April, 2026), there are 245 supply contracts for a total contracted capacity of 1,550 kW. This information is detailed in the following table:

VILLAGE	Number of supply contracts	Contracted power (kW)
Munébrega	12	197.00
Codos	1	5.50
Calatayud	3	77.36
Ruesca	17	67.96
Miedes de Aragón	10	52.21
Carenas	12	71.93
Bubierca	31	142.68
Pozuel de Ariza	8	31.45
Maluenda	26	243.76
Cervera de la Cañada	9	39.15
Valtorres	20	85.45
Ariza	11	87.74
Belmonte	15	92.86
Medinaceli	17	80.19
Torrijo de la Cañada	3	12.10
Mediavega	3	34.36
Others	47	228.25
TOTAL	245	1,549.95

Both on the JALON project website (<https://jalon-ce.eu>) and on the CERCA website (<https://cercaenergia.com>), as well as on their respective social networks, you can find photo reports and videos about these photovoltaic projects.

Figure 5: JALON partners and CERCA participants in Valtorres (October 2024)